

AN ANALYSIS OF THE PRESCHOOL TEACHERS' VIEWS ON ALPHA GENERATIONⁱ

Çiğdem Apaydinⁱⁱⁱ,

Feyza Kaya

¹Assoc. Prof. Dr.,

Akdeniz University,

Faculty of Education,

Turkey

²Math Teacher,

High School,

Turkey

Abstract:

This research aims to identify the characteristics of alpha generation students from the lens of pre-school teachers. In this regard, the research questioned whether there was a difference between alpha generation and Z generation students in terms of some variables. Besides, the class management techniques used for both generations and the change in parent profiles were discussed comparatively. The working group consisted of twelve teachers working at private preschool schools in Antalya. Having a qualitative research design, this research used content analysis method during data analysis. The research findings revealed that the negative characteristics of alpha generation were more than positive characteristics. Alpha generation was found to exhibit behaviors such as being more curious, free from any rules, being more ill-tempered, more mobile and more self-centred than Z generation; moreover, they also had high self-esteem, and they were more emotional and more conscious. In terms of communication, Alpha generation was also determined to be more closed and behave more individually than Z generation. Considering classroom management techniques, preschool teachers were found to use the reconstructive approach for the alpha generation and traditional classroom management techniques for Z generation. The research findings also indicated that alpha generation parents were more conscious and sensitive than Z generation parents. However, the alpha generation parents were noted to have a negative point of view towards the preschool teachers.

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ⁱⁱ Correspondence: email: cigdemapaydin@akdeniz.edu.tr

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1. Introduction

The rapid development in information and technology, especially the existence of the internet and various websites and the content it contains, has led to the change of mindset and behaviour within society. Ramadlani and Wibisono (2017) stressed that the change of each generation's mindset induces their behaviours to shift positively or negatively. Along with this change, the concept of cyberspace has emerged and changes have occurred in the individual, social and community point of views. Considering the individual level, a fundamental change towards cyberspace has been created, and each individual in the virtual world could be divided into infinite numbers of identities. Such fake identities can cause individuals to demonstrate numbers of unethical behaviours such as editing photo, spreading hoaxes anonymously and taking peoples' photos without any permission as well as sharing it in social media, etc. These actions can be regarded as cybercrimes. (Ramadlani, 2016:45). In cyberspace (virtual reality), individuals can establish close ties with people they have never met before, which leads to social deterioration. At the community level, the presence of cyberspace is related to the creation of a community model which is known as the digital and open democratic community. Rheingold (2000) specified this as the "*imaginary community*". This phenomenon arises in the existence of the younger generation, particularly *the alpha generation (net generation)*.

Alpha generation is a generation that is born after the Z generation. The entire Alpha generation is the first generation holding individuals born in the 21st century. In the study conducted on the post-Z generation in 2015, McCrindle identified that the participants called this generation as "*Generation Alpha*" (cited in Nagy and Kölcsey 2017). Stefanov, Terziev and Banabakova (2018) used the term "*homo tabletus*" for this generation. This generation is considered to have been born in the 2010-2025 period. Those in alpha generation include infants, babies and those who are not yet born. Alpha generation, starting to learn at an early age, becomes a higher educated generation compared to the other ones. The fun and education of this generation depend largely on screens; moreover, it will be realized over time what kind of codes can be generated for global decision makers related to the exposure to the screen. The iPad was launched in 2010, when the eldest of this generation was born, and Instagram took its place on social channels and "app" became the word of the year. Therefore, the fixed screen experience of past generations is not able to address their fluid and fully mobile experiences. Screenager is a distinctive feature of this generation (Kaynak, 2017).

What is the most significant about this generation is the digital environment into which they are born. Technology, parents, educators and other social interactions influence their everyday lives. The concept of "connection" is central to this generation, even more important than the previous Generation Z (Tootell, Freeman & Freeman, 2014, p. 82). In general, the characteristics of this generation can be summarized as

dependencies on screens and touch screen world. Carter (2016) noted that this generation would rather communicate visually through images and audios than type messages, and they need much more attention as they are filthily pampered by their parents. He added that this generation is a technology literate generation. Barkowitz (2016) coined alpha generation as creative, Holroyd (2011) stated that the alpha generation learn in a longer period of time despite close interaction with online learning, and they grow up rapidly with the effect of technology. The researcher indicated that this generation is surrounded by material concepts and their ability to overcome problems is high. The characteristics of the alpha generation are presented by the researchers as follows (Schawbell, 2014; Barkowitz, 2016; Ramadlani and Wibisono, 2017).

Table 1: The characteristics of alpha generation

Schawbell (2014)	Barkowitz (2016)	Ramadlani ve Wibisono (2017)
More entrepreneurial	They hate sharing.	They have entrepreneurial soul due to the ability to access the information, people, and the power age members.
Technology savvy	They are quite mobile.	They have more smart technology.
They do not know the world without social networking.	They do not care about privacy They have the narcissistic and exhibitionistic tendencies.	They trust in social media.
They prefer online shopping.	They don't play by the rules.	They prefer to shop online.
They rarely have human contact while communicating.	They dislike any boundaries.	They barely do physical contact in communicating with people.
They are extremely coddled by their X and Y generation parents.	They prefer healthy life.	Although they can still communicate through social media, they show solitude behaviour.
They are extremely influenced by their X and Y generation parents.	They like carbohydrates.	They are more pampered by their X and Y generation parents.
They have a high level of skills for overcoming challenges.	They eschew organized religion.	They are more influenced by their X and Y generation parents.
They are better educated.	They don't like excessive consumption. They are reinventing wearables.	They can face great challenges.
They are self-sufficient.	They like to overcome sensational things.	They are self-sufficient.
	They repeat the same thing for pleasure.	They handle with environmental and social problems.
	They don't do two tasks at once.	
	They live in the moment and want everything now.	
	They are constantly changing.	

Contrary to Barkowitz and Ramadlani & Wibisono's negative point of views towards alpha generation, Schawbel (2014) positively considered alpha generation as the one that has far more opportunities and challenges. Having evaluated alpha generation with a critical eye, Nagy and Kölcsey (2017) emphasized that the characteristics attributed to the alpha generation involve prognosis, that is, estimations. However, Bennett, Maton, and Kervin (2008) argued that the alpha generation is a different "*digital natives*" generation and that education needs to be fundamentally changed in order to meet the needs of "*digital natives*".

Nagy and Kölcsey (2017) pointed out that the naming and identification of alpha generation is mostly for marketing purposes and that we need to know more about alpha generation. As stated by Nagy and Kölcsey (2017) in general terms, there are no detailed studies specifically conducted on alpha generation in the relevant literature. In this regard, this research aims to be the source of information regarding alpha generation. Besides, this research also seeks to identify the characteristics of the alpha generation, its differences from the digitally integrated generation Z, parent profile, and the differences in the classroom management techniques used by teachers in their classes.

Carter (2016) mentioned that approximately 9,000 alpha babies are born every day in the USA. He also reported that children under twelve influence parental purchases between [\\$130 to \\$670](#) a year in total. In 2050, the alpha generation population in America is estimated to reach 35 million. This situation does not differ across Turkey. According to the results of the Turkey Statistical Institute (TSI) Address Based Population Registration System (ABPRS) in 2017, the alpha generation population will reach 26 million in 2040, which constitutes approximately 26% of the country's population. As can be seen, policies need to be developed in terms of education for alpha generation. Prensky (2001a) stated that most teachers lack the technological fluency of the alpha generation in the present order and are almost entirely alien to their skills. Prensky (2001a) implied that most of the teachers lack the technological fluency of the alpha generation in the present order and they are almost totally foreign to the skills they have. The discrepancy between the technological skills and interests of the Alpha generation and the educators' uncomplicated and limited use of technology can create alienation and disaffection among students (Prensky, 2005a). With the aim of overcoming these difficulties, professional development and evaluation in curriculum, pedagogy and teacher education require radical changes. Thus, this research serves as a reference for policy development towards alpha generation.

2. Method

2.1 Research Design

This is a case study based on the qualitative research model. Qualitative case study is an empirical research method that (1) examines a contemporary phenomenon within its real life context, (2) the boundaries between phenomenon and its content are not clearly evident (3) relies on multiple sources of evidence or data (Yin, 1984, p.23, Cited in

Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2005: 277). This research employed a holistic single-case study design. Holistic single-case represents a single unit of analysis (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2005: 290).

2.2 Working group

The research population consisted of preschool teachers working in private kindergartens in the central districts of Antalya province during the spring semester of 2018-2019.

The research population is the accessible group. A holistic context that can represent all the diversity, differences and richness in the population is tried to be obtained since there is no generalization concern in qualitative researches. Therefore, 'purposive sampling' model is used in qualitative researches. The main aim of this method is to gather detailed data from particular settings, persons, or activities (Maxwell, 1996). The research utilized convenience sampling, one of the purposive sampling methods. The willingness of preschool teachers was taken into consideration during the interviews. The convenience sampling case method provides speed and easiness to the research. In this method, the researcher chooses a situation that is close and easy to access (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2005).

The mean age of the participants was determined to be 29.2. The participants consisted of 12 female preschool teachers. The mean of teachers' seniority was identified as approximately 9.08 year. Among the participants, 6 were in private kindergarten and 6 were in preschool.

2.3 Data Collection Tool

This research deployed a semi-structured individual interview form as a data collection tool. The interview form is prepared to obtain the same kind of information from different people by addressing similar subjects (Patton, 1987, 111). The most significant opportunity that the semi-structured interview technique offers to the researcher is that it provides more systematic and comparable information since the interview is conducted in accordance with the interview protocol prepared in advance (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2005). With a view to ensuring the internal validity of the semi-structured interview form, the form was prepared after the conceptual framework was prepared, the related literature was conducted, and the experts' opinions were taken after the preliminary interviews were performed. In order for the data obtained from the interviews to be effective and efficient, an interview form consisting of five questions was prepared by taking into consideration that the questions are easy to understand, specific, open-ended and far from any direction. The first part of the interview form includes questions regarding the participants' demographic information and the second part holds questions about the subject.

2.4 Interviews and Research Data Collection

Prior to starting the interviews, the required permission was taken from Akdeniz University the Social and Humanities Ethics Committee and Antalya Provincial Directorate of National Education through Akdeniz University Institute of Educational

Sciences. Negotiations were conducted with the administrators and preschool teachers working in the kindergartens and preschools within the central boundaries of Antalya, and they were informed that the names of the teachers and administrators willing to participate in the research would be kept confidential and would be coded in the research. Interview forms were handed to the teachers and administrators willing to participate in the research by the researchers themselves. The participants themselves filled the interview forms in writing. Researchers did not intervene in this process. All ethical processes were taken into account during the interviews.

2.5 Data Analysis

The obtained data were textualized by the researcher through use of Microsoft Word 2010 program. The data were coded and the data referring to each research question were grouped in themselves, which is called as a descriptive analysis. Subsequently, content analysis was used for in-depth data analysis with the help of the experts' views. Content analysis is defined as *"a flexible research tool applicable to any form of communication and focusing on the content of a text (Cavanagh, 1997); the objective and systematic meaning of the content (Berelson, 1952)"* (cited in Kızıltepe, 2017, p. 253). In content analysis, similar data are brought together, gathered under certain concepts and themes, and interpreted in a meaningful way. The aim of the content analysis is to reach concepts and relationships that can explain the collected data (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2005).

The elicited data were analyzed through frequency analysis within content analysis. The responses of the teachers and administrators were tried to be classified through frequency analysis technique. According to the frequency of teachers' responses, a thematic classification under categories and frequency and tables depending on this thematic classification were analyzed. The study also offered direct quotes from the participants' views. Teachers were coded depending on the school names and types. The number appointed to the teacher was indicated at the end of the coding.

2.6 Validity and Reliability

In qualitative research, "validity" is related to the accuracy of scientific findings and, reliability is the repeatability of scientific findings. In this regard, the following applications were carried out in order to increase the validity and reliability of the research.

- a) To increase the internal validity of the research; a conceptual framework was developed as a result of the literature review while developing the interview form. Integration between the themes and sub-themes constituting the themes and the relationship of each theme with the others were ensured in the content analysis. Besides, the participant confirmation was provided after the findings and comments were confirmed with the data sources. On the other hand, signing the agreement that the information recorded in the interviews would only be used for scientific purposes and the names would be coded during reporting process are paramount in ensuring mutual trust. Thus, the data collected during the interview process were expected to reflect the real situation.

- b) The research process and what has been done in this process were explained in detail so as to increase the external validity (transferability) of the research. In this context, the research design, working group, data collection tool, data collection process, data analysis were presented in detail. Interviews were conducted with the participants on a voluntary basis and a purposive sampling method was used to reveal the varying characteristics of phenomenon and phenomena. The findings were interpreted and discussed in a way to contribute to the educational management literature.
- c) In order to increase the internal reliability (consistency) of the research, all the findings obtained from the participants were given directly without any comment.
- d) All data collection tools, raw data, codifications made during the analysis and perceptions, notes, writings and inferences that form the basis of the report were presented to an expert's opinion for the purpose of increasing the external reliability (confirmability) of the research.

3. Findings

3.1 Findings Related to the Characteristics of Alpha Generation

The participants were of the view that the distinctive characteristics of alpha generation are as follows (Table 1). Table 1 depicts that the negative behaviour styles of alpha generation are much more than positive behaviors. As can be seen in Table 1, participants perceive technology addiction, egocentricism and tendency to violence as negative characteristics of alpha generation. One participant expressed his/her view on the technology addiction of the Alpha generation as *"The students we educate in the academic year lack attention, and they are dissatisfied as well as unhappy, that is, tablet and phone addicted children (Pa1t)*, while another participant mentioned that *"More television and the Internet, they play more games and sleep"* (Sska4t). The participants associated technology addiction with a tablet, phone, internet, television or digital media. The participants also indicated that technology-dependent alpha-generation students have a greater tendency to violence. One participant explained this situation as *"Children who spend a lot of time with technology tend to be more violent"* (Sk2t). Another negative characteristic of alpha generation is that they are egocentric. One participant stated alpha generation's disability to empathize with friends referring to the fact that *"they are self-centred with a sense of stubbornness [...]"* (Pa2t).

Table 1: The characteristics of Alpha generation

Negative characteristics	n	Positive characteristics	n
Technology addict	7	High level of perception	3
More tendency to violence	4	Tapping out with music	2
Egocentric	4	Ability to use numbers effectively	2
Limited social communication	2	Careful	2
Obstinate	2	Emotional	2
Ill-tempered	2	Elaborative	1
Disobedience to the rules	1	Making visual research	1

Lack of Problem solving skills	1	Liking of showing oneself	1
Impatient	1	Good verbal communication	1
Energetic	1	Creative	1
Lack of attention	1	Determined	1
Insatiable	1	Curious to learn	1
Unhappy	1	Having a wide perspective towards events	1
Less book reading	1		
Introverted	1		
Poor language development	1		
Total	31	Total	19

The most notable positive characteristics of alpha generation are having high levels of perception, tapping out with music, effective use of numbers, being careful and emotional (Table 1). One participant stating Alpha generation has high perception level said that *“My students this year are very active, their perceptions are high [...]”* (Ek2t); another participants mentioned that *“they are creative, determined, open to learning”* (Sk1t). The other positive characteristics adopted by alpha generation were determined as the ability to tap out with music and effective use of numbers. One participant related to the issue emphasized that *“[...] is a generation that uses numbers effectively, is able to make visual research, and has the ability to tap out with music”* (Bk1t). Having indicated that the Alpha generation is quite careful, one participant explained the situation as *“they are more careful, and they are aware of the smallest details”* (Sska3öt), while another participant emphasised the generation’s being emotional with such words *“Some are very emotional while others are suppress all their emotions and may remain unresponsive”* (Sk2t).

3.2 Findings Related to the Comparison of Z Generation Students and Alpha Generation Students in terms of Behaviour, Personal Characteristics, Academic Competence, Relationship with Technology, Communication Skills, Relationships with Friends and Out-of-Class Behaviors

Table 2 presents the comparison of alpha generation students and Z generation students in terms of behaviour, personal characteristics, academic competence, relationship with technology, communication skills, relationships with friends and out-of-school behaviors. Only two participants mentioned that there was no significant difference between Z generation and alpha generation. The participants explained that *“There are no significant differences with the previous period”* (Ek1t and Ek2t).

The other participants were of the opinion that there are distinguishing features between alpha and Z generations. According to Table 2, alpha generation students were identified to have more responsive behaviours and they were more willing to unethical behaviors compared to Z generation students. For instance, the participants reported that alpha generation students are more active, more ill-tempered, more stubborn, and angrier than the Z generation (Table 2). One participant signified that *“Alpha generation is more mobile than Z generation, it seems that the rate of using violence and playing games with violence is very high and the rate of disagreement is much higher”* (Ek2t). One participant talking about more ill-tempered Alpha generation students said, *“They are much more ego-*

centric, we are encountering a group that is increasingly aggressive” (Sska2t); furthermore, another participant referred to this situation as “Their sense of self is high, they can get angry immediately and become more ill-tempered” (Sk1t). The research findings revealed that alpha generation students are more egocentric considering their personal characteristics. One participant gave information about the personal characteristics of the students as “More egocentricists” (Sk1ö). A participant who stated that alpha generation students had higher self-confidence compared to Z generation indicated that “They have more self-confidence in communicating with people than Z generation” (Bk1t). A participant emphasized that the alpha generation was more emotional with these words, “They are more emotional and repartee” (Sska1t).

Given their academic competence, alpha generation students were determined have more than one knowledge compared to Z generation students, they make differences in the games they have established, they are more open to learning and their social intelligence is limited, although their numerical intelligence is high (Table 2). The participant noted that “S/He has a lot of knowledge, but they starve for interest and love” (Sska2t).

Both generations were identified to have a tendency towards technology. The participants finalized that alpha generation had a higher level of interest. A participant comparing both generations in relation to technology explained the situation as “In the previous generation, children were more familiar with the concept of street playing outside. However, the current generation consist of children who use technology more and do not leave the house [...]” (Pa2t).

Table 2: Comparison of Z Generation and Alpha Generation in Terms of Some Variables

Variables	The characteristics of Z generation	n	The characteristics of alpha generation	n
In terms of behaviour	Curious	4	More curious	4
	Ill-tempered, stubborn, angry	3	More ill-tempered, stubborn, angrier	4
	Introvert	2	More introvert	1
	Obey the rules	2	Free from any rule	3
	Active	2	More active	2
	Respectful	2	Limited level of respect	2
	Sharing	2	Limited level of sharing behaviour	2
	Waiting for support from the environment	1	Self-sufficient	2
In terms of personal characteristics	Adapt to the environment	1	Having adaptation problem	1
	Egocentric	5	More egocentric	6
	Self-confident	3	More self-confident	3
	Emotional	3	More emotional	3
	Conscious	2	More conscious	3
	Watching cartoons	2	Watching the programs including violence	3
	Violent	2	More tendency to violence	2
	Being able to empathize	2	Limited empathy	2
	Repartee	2	More repartee	2

	Stable development	1	Rapid development	1
	Non-libertarian	1	Fond of freedom	1
	Compliance with authority	1	Denial of authority	1
	Not having attention problems	1	Having attention problems	1
In terms of academic competence	Knowledgeable	3	Having more knowledge	3
	Playing classical games	3	Making a difference in the games they set up	3
	Open to learning	2	More open to learning	2
	Normal numerical intelligence	2	Higher level of numerical intelligence	2
	Normal verbal intelligence	2	Limited verbal intelligence	2
	Limited readiness levels	1	Sufficient readiness levels	1
	Understanding easily	2	Understanding more easily	2
In terms of the relation with technology	Technological	10	More technological	10
	Low level of technology dependency	9	High level of technology dependency	9
In terms of communication skills	Social	4	Asocial	4
	Effective communication with the environment	1	Effective communication with the environment at a high level	1
	Avoid using imperative statements	1	Use of imperative statement more	1
	Low foreign language use	1	More foreign language use	1
In terms of relationship with friends	Establishing positive relationships with peers	11	Peer conflict	11
	Good communication with friends	7	Difficulty in communicating with friends	7
	Equality between friends	1	Desire for being a leader	1
	More respectful to each other's private areas	1	Limited respect for private area	1
In terms of out-of-class behaviors	Performing a given task in earnest	1	Escaping from duty and responsibility	1
	Growing up by playing games outside, familiar with the street	1	Not leaving the house	2
	Obey the ethical rules	1	Non-compliance with ethical rules	1
	Similar behaviors both in the classroom environment and outside	1	Different behaviors both in the classroom environment and outside (quiet in the class while very naughty outside)	1

When two generations were evaluated in terms of communication skills and relations with friends, Z generation was found to possess higher communication skills than alpha generation. The findings also suggested that the alpha generation is open to development in terms of communication skills such as having peer conflict, having difficulty in communicating with friends, showing leadership rather than sharing, and exhibiting limited behaviors regarding respect for the private area. The following extracts were drawn from the interviews with the teachers.

They are more confident in communicating with people than the Z generation. Self-centeredness and the desire for becoming a leader are at the forefront. They try to express themselves without waiting for a turn to speak while communicating with each other (Bk1t).

"[...] Children with social isolation and lack of empathy, peer conflict, lack of communication, verbal communication skills." (Bk2t).

"[...] It seems that the rate of disagreement among them is much higher" (Ek2t).

"[...] Considering their close ties with technology in social relations, they are far behind in communication, not often responding to what is said" (Sska1t).

"[...] The feeling of sharing is weak, they get bored quickly" (Sk1t).

"Z generation had good relations with almost everyone with cheerful and sweet talk. They were more respectful to each other's private areas." (Sk2t).

As for out-of-class behaviors; the participants explained that the Z generation performed the tasks by taking responsibility and that their compliance with ethical principles and street recognition levels were high, and that their out and in class behaviors were more compatible than alpha generation. One participant stated that *"I observe that there is a transition from a student group (Z generation) who respects the rules and fulfils the assigned task with a happy life to a student group (alpha generation) which is repartee escaping duties and responsibilities" (Pa1t)*. Another participant considered that *"Their behaviours outside were also close to their status in the classroom. However, in this generation (alpha generation), the harmonious child in the classroom escapes the responsibilities outside the classroom" (Sk2t)*. One participant concluded that the alpha generation is indeed social, but children are not able to communicate with the environment due to the increasing violence in the society, and hence they could not communicate with the environment. The participant explained this situation as follows *"They are more open, but they are constrained by the family and the environment because of increasing violence in the community and abuse of children" (Pa1t)*.

3.3 Findings Related to the Differences between Alpha and Z Generation in terms of the Classroom Management Techniques

Table 3 displays the differences in terms of classroom management techniques used by teachers. Accordingly, while teachers use classroom management techniques based upon the reconstructive approach for alpha generation, they prefer to use more traditional methods for Z generation. In particular, alpha generation's tendency to the use of technology has an effect on teachers' teaching. One participant clarified that *"It may be a bit more difficult to get attention due to the alpha generation's technology addiction. It is inevitable to use materials and to incorporate technology into the classroom" (Ek1ö)*. Another participant

expressing his/her views on traditional classroom management techniques said, *“Some more traditional classroom management techniques can be used for Z generation compared to alpha generation”* (Bk1t). Another participant explained the changes in classroom management techniques with the following words:

“In the classroom methods we used, while the students pay more attention to the teacher-centred lesson, but now I observe that they are student-centred and distracted very quickly; moreover they have low concentration.” (Pa1t)

The participants were of the view that alpha generation expects the use of visual, auditory and kinaesthetic tools in classroom management. They also believed that alpha generation students are distracted more easily while Z generation listen to the teacher more careful. The following are the expressions obtained from participants' views:

“Alpha generation is addicted to technology and it takes some time to focus their attention on the lesson. Using audio-visual material and incorporating technology in the classroom increases class participation.” (Ek2t)

“Technology attracts alpha generation's attention as they were born with the concept of technology, and I think activities are more effective with video, music, animation.” (Sska3t)

“I used to make use of books, pictures, and so on. But now we use the Internet.” (Sska4t)

Table 3: The Comparison of Z Generation and Alpha Generation
in Terms of Classroom Management Techniques

Generations	Themes	Sub-themes	n
Alfa Generation	Reconstruction perspective	Integration of technology into the lesson	10
		Student-centred classroom management	5
		Using visual, auditory and mechanical classroom management techniques	5
		Prevention of distractions in the classroom	4
		Address multiple sensory organs through instruction techniques	3
		Having a learning environment open to innovation	1
		Allowing students to be active in class	1
		Appropriateness to the students' individual and social needs	1
		Increasing students' motivation by using technology	1
		Conducting group activities instead of individual activities	1
Z Generation	Traditional classroom management perspective	Giving feedback	1
		Use of traditional classroom management techniques	2
		Teacher-centred teaching	2
		Listen to the lesson more carefully	1
		High participation in the lesson	1
		Use of materials available in daily life	1
Use of pictures and similar materials	1		

Another factor that participants stated was that the instruction techniques should be constructed to address more than one sense in classroom management for alpha generation students. One of the participants implied that *"I think they want to use technology more. It becomes more effective and interesting if I teach animals with the animation documentary"* (Sska3t). Another participant (Sska4t) stated that it is sufficient for Z generation students to use painting and similar materials as a classroom management technique.

4.4 Findings Related to the Changes in Parent Profiles (Behaviour, Communication Style, etc.)

Four participants concluded that there was no change in the students' parent profiles, while eight of them implied vice versa. Table 4 presents the findings regarding the changes in the students' parent profiles. The participants ruminated that the parents of the alpha generation are trying to improve themselves by observing the generation gap with the students. The related teachers' views are exemplified in the following quotes:

"Parents are trying to develop themselves in line with the needs of children, as required by the age. They compare their own generations with their children, observe the differences and act in this regard." (Bk1t).

"Parent profile trying to respond to the personal and social needs of the children who have the ability to set limits." (Bk2t)

The participants conceived that another change in the parent profile derives from the perspective towards the teacher. They put forward that parents consider teachers as pupils' caretakers and thus respect, love and tolerance towards teachers decrease. Therefore, the student is adversely affected by this situation and exhibits more responsive behaviors to the teacher. One participant stressed that *"The parent who considers teacher not as an educator, but as a caretaker"* (Pa1t). Another participant criticized that *"Parents always put the blame on the teacher. Due to the parents' lack of understanding and tolerance, children imitate what they see, not what they say"* (Sska1t). The participants of the research also implied that the alpha generation parents reject the negative aspects of the children and that they thought their children were excellent. One participant complained that *"Recently, there existed a parent profile thinking that the student is always right, and that teachers are guilty"* (Pa1t). Another participant explains the situation in the following extract.

Obviously, if parents stop believing that both they and their children are perfect, look their children from the eyes of a teacher, we can communicate more easily. We have great difficulty as they reject their children's negative characteristics (Sska3t).

Table 4: The changes in parent profile

The change observed in parent profile	f
Parents' efforts to improve themselves by observing the generation gap with students	4
Parents see teachers as pupils' caretakers	3
Parents have the understanding that "the student is always right, the teacher is guilty"	2
Parents' respect, love and tolerance towards teachers decrease	2
Parents' refusal to see the negative aspects of their children	2
Students tread in their parents' negative attitudes toward teachers	1
Parents have high expectations from the teacher	1
Parents think their children are perfect	1
Parents see the school as a place to spend time	1

Having stated that the alpha generation parents' expectations from the teachers were high, one participant mentioned that *"Yes, of course I observe, in that, when there is a possible negativity, there is no "acceptance"; we sometimes feel compressed by parents due to high expectation"* (Sk1t). Besides, another participant said that parents see schools as a place to spend time with such words as *"There are parents who send the child to spend time while they are at work rather than learn something. To illustrate, the child can come to school even when s/he is sick"* (Sk2t).

4. Conclusion and Discussion

The relevant literature welcomes both the researchers who claim that there is no alpha generation and those insisting on the presence of a different generation. This research focuses on whether the alpha generation differs from the Z generation. In this regard, the views of the preschool teachers were taken into consideration. In general, teachers were of the view that there are distinctive features between Z generation and alpha generation students.

Based upon the research findings, alpha generation was identified to have positive characteristics such as tendency towards violence, being egocentric, having limited social communication along with negative behaviours like higher perception levels, tapping out with music and using numbers effectively. Bejtkovský (2016) noted that alpha generation students are highly pampered by parents of X and Y generations and are more influenced by their families. Thus, the negative attitudes of the families in alpha generation's behaviors may lead to negative effects on alpha generation. Andrea, Gabriella and Tímea (2016) stated that the Z generation, the previous generation of the alpha generation, was born in the world of technology and felt good about it. The Z generation is almost constantly in an online life. The characteristics of this generation include practicality, intelligent and courageous, though not wise, leadership, impatient, agile and strong desire for new challenges. The researchers defined Z generation as individuals who have a virtual and superficial perspective, who do not have a sense of commitment, who are satisfied with what they have and who live in the present. This generation reacts quickly and relies on intuition. The present research determined that alpha generation are more prone to being responsive and exhibiting unethical behaviors

along with having these characteristics mentioned above, which is parallel to the Z generation. For instance, this research suggested that alpha generation exhibited negative behaviors such as limited respect for private area, being angrier and more ill-tempered.

They were found to be more emotional, more conscious and more confident in terms of personal characteristics. Besides, they could access more knowledge more quickly due to their excessive dependence on technology, which makes them freer and more creative individuals. Brown (2000) stressed that students can listen to music, talk on mobile phones and use computers simultaneously, that is multiprocessing, nowadays. It is also claimed that the Alpha generation is accustomed to high-speed learning, making random connections, processing visual and dynamic information, and learning through game-based activities (Prensky, 2001a). Findings supporting Brown (2000) and Prensky (2001a)'s views were obtained in the current research. Accordingly, another finding of the study was the presence of difference in terms of classroom management techniques. Preschool teachers admitted that they use more traditional classroom management techniques for Z generation while more modern techniques for the alpha generation. Teachers stated that alpha generation students' deep interest in technology is reflected in their teaching. Therefore, the pre-school teachers were determined to teach and perform classroom management with a constructivist approach. Tapscott (1998) concluded that the old didactic teaching approach does not meet the intellectual, social, motivational and emotional needs of the new generation. Brown (2000) unveiled that students prefer discovery-based learning, which enables them to explore and actively test and generate knowledge from ideas arising from multitasking skills. Prensky (2005a) clarified that the technology based lifestyles of the alpha generation are not in harmony with the limited use of technology by teachers. Prensky (2001a, p.3) explained this as "*the biggest single problem facing education today*". This is the proof that alpha generation is growing with advanced knowledge and skills related to information technologies. Thus, they hold certain learning preferences and styles unlike previous generations. This research confirms the findings of those who claim that the alpha generation learn differently from previous generations (Tapscott, 1998; Brown, 2000; Prensky, 2001; Kırpık and Akdemir, 2018).

On the other, the distinctive characteristics of alpha generation included limited social communication due to their dependence on technology, their tendency to work individually rather than teamwork, exhibition of leadership behaviors rather than being collaborative. The research findings also suggested that the alpha generation is freer from any rule and escapes from the responsibilities in terms of out-of-class behaviors. Erbay (2017) described this generation as having all the information without deepening and questioning and getting bored easily. Bejtkovský (2016) found that the characteristics of alpha generation involve; they have less human contact than previous generations, they will be more self-sufficient and better educated. Similar findings also emerged in this research.

Another research finding was related to the parents. Preschool teachers thought that the alpha generation parents change compared to the X, Y and Z generation parents, that they are more open to development and learning, and that their perspective towards

teacher is more negative than the X, Y and Z generation parents even though the expectation from the teacher increases. Serinik (2019) asserted that the alpha generation will be fond of their families. Therefore, parents' negative point of view reflects on the student and thus leading to undesired behaviors towards the teacher. Parents' high expectations from teachers put teachers under pressure and make it difficult for teachers to provide accurate information about the students.

There is a need for conducting a research in the field of cognitive psychology based upon the results that alpha generation can make multiprocessing with teachers' observations and experiences. Whether such a feature exists or it provides benefits to the person should be examined. Structural reforms are needed in the education system in order to meet the needs of the alpha generation having sophisticated technology skills. Although there is no strong evidence that the alpha generation has a distinct learning style, this research may be a clue to this claim.

About the Author

Çiğdem Apaydin is an Assoc. Prof. Dr. in Departments of Educational Sciences at the University of Akdeniz, Antalya, Turkey, where she teaches a lecture and courses in qualitative research and educational administration undergraduate and graduate students. She has a PhD in Educational Administration. Her areas of interest include qualitative research, higher education, workaholic, work-life balance.

Şerife Feyza Kaya is a math teacher as a private high school, Antalya, Turkey. She has a master degree in Educational Administration.

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